

COL₂X₂ type of complexes show two absorption bands ~16.5 (950) and ~8.5 (200) k.k. region attributable to ⁴A₂→⁴T_{1g} (P) and ⁴A₂→⁴T₁ (F) transitions respectively suggesting a tetrahedral stereochemistry of these complexes supported by their magnetic moment data. Complexes of the composition CoX₂L₄ also show two absorption bands ~18. (35) and 8.2 (20) k.k. region assignable to ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{1g}(P) and ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{2g}(F) transitions respectively. On the basis of the spectral bands and their magnetic moments a spin free octahedral configuration is indicated for these complexes supported by earlier observation⁹. All the nickel(II) complexes give rise to three absorption bands ~8.5-9.1 (6), 13.3-13.5 (6) and 24.1-24.5 (14) k.k. regions due to ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{2g}(F), ³T_{1g}(F) and ³T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively and a possible spin free octahedral stereochemistry is suggested¹⁰ for these complexes. Copper(II) halide complexes show one broad band ~14.8-15.1 (38) k.k. region and the thiocyanate complex shows one band at 17.8 (42) k.k. region. Presumably the halide complexes have a distorted octahedral configuration¹¹ whereas the thiocyanate complex is planar. Two bands are observed in case of manganese(II) complexes ~27.5 and 24.6 k.k. regions suggesting¹² an octahedral environment about the metal ion. On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral studies zinc and cadmium complexes have a possible tetrahedral geometry.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance and Research & Development Department, Hindustan Photo Films Ltd., Ootacamond for recording the I. R. spectra.

References

1. C. D. RAO and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* (London), 1977, **39**, 689.
2. C. D. RAO, S. GURU and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1240.
3. P. K. PANDA and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* (London), (In Press).
4. B. G. RAMSEY and J. G. GRASSELLI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1969, **3**, 503.
5. J. REEDIJIK, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **5**, 687.
6. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER, "Spectrometric Identification of Inorganic Compounds" (John Wiley, New York), 1967.
7. J. R. FERRARO, "Low Frequency Vibrations of Inorganic and Co-ordination Compounds", (Plenum Press), 1971.
8. A. TRAMER, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1962, **59**, 232.
9. D. P. GRADDON and E. C. WATTON, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1965, **18**, 507.
10. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", (Wiley Eastern, New Delhi), 1976.
11. A. B. P. LEVER "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy" (Elsevier, Amsterdam), 1968.
12. S. K. MADAN and J. A. STURR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 1669.

Unstable Chromium(III) Chlorate

M. R. UDUPA

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology,
Madras-600 036, India

Manuscript received 29 October 1979,
accepted 22 December 1979

PERCHLORATES and chlorates are powerful oxidizing agents and the thermal decomposition of intimate mixtures of chromium(III) oxide and LiClO₄, TiClO₄, KClO₄ and KClO₃ resulted in the formation of metal dichromates. Chromium(III) perchlorate hexahydrate on thermolysis⁵ gives chromium(VI) oxide and chromyl chloride. In this context, it was thought interesting to study the thermal behaviour of chromium(III) chlorate and to identify the decomposition products in order to find out whether Cr(III) is oxidized into Cr(VI) by the chlorate moiety. No information is available in the literature about the preparation and existence of this compound. In this note is reported the attempted method of isolation of Cr(ClO₃)₃ and its immediate oxidation to Cr(VI).

Experimental

10 m moles (6.622 g) of Cr₂(SO₄)₃·15H₂O are dissolved in 100 ml water and to which is added a solution containing 30 m moles (9.667 g) of Ba(ClO₃)₂·H₂O in 100 ml water. The contents are stirred for 15 min and the precipitated BaSO₄ is filtered. The filtrate containing Cr(ClO₃)₃ solution is checked for Cr(III) content by iodometry after oxidizing Cr(III) with potassium peroxydisulphate⁶. A known amount of the Cr(ClO₃)₃ solution was taken in a petri dish and was evaporated on a water bath. Blue colour of the solution persisted till the complete evaporation of water and suddenly the thick liquid turned into a red mass. The electronic spectrum was recorded on a Carl Zeiss DMR 21 recording spectrometer and the infrared spectrum was taken on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrometer in nujol mull. The X-ray powder photograph was taken using CuK α radiation and Debye-Scherrer camera of diameter 11.46 cm.

Results and Discussion

The red mass obtained, is found to be hygroscopic and its electronic spectrum in water exhibited absorptions at 23.0, 28.8 and 39.0 kK, which are the characteristic of [CrO₅(OH)]⁻ species⁷. The infrared spectrum showed absorption bands at (cm⁻¹) 975s and 850w, b which are due⁸ to CrO₃. Further, the X-ray powder patterns of the solid showed the most intense lines at (Å) 4.23, 3.40 and 3.33 which correspond⁹ to CrO₃. Further confirmation of the solid was achieved by chemical analysis. Known amount of Cr(ClO₃)₃ solution was taken in an all-glass apparatus, with a provision to collect the liberated

gases, and heated to 100°. The evolved gases during the concentration and conversion to CrO₃ was collected in a flask containing water. If Cr(III) oxidized as gaseous CrO₂Cl₂, it is hydrolyzed and Cr(VI) is determined iodometrically after boiling off the dissolved chlorine in the solution. Cr(IV) is also determined in the residual red mass. The analytical results are given in Table 1, which suggest

TABLE 1—DATA ON ANALYSIS OF CHROMIUM

(Cr ³⁺ + 3ClO ₃ ⁻) taken (m mole)	Found (m mo'e)		Molar ratio CrO ₃ /CrO ₂ Cl
	CrO ₃	CrO ₂ Cl ₂	
0.10	0.032	0.066	2.06
0.15	0.051	0.102	2.00
0.25	0.085	0.172	2.02

that 2/3 of Cr(III) is oxidized into CrO₃ and the remaining one-third to CrO₂Cl₂. The reaction scheme is given as

Slow evaporation of chromium(III) chlorate solution at room temperature, either keeping at open atmosphere or in a desiccator also resulted in the formation of CrO₃ after several days. Cr(VI) also formed in solution on boiling the acidified Cr(ClO₃)₃ solution. The fact that Cr(VI) formed after the removal of water from the chromium chlorate solution and only by boiling the acidified solution indicates that Cr(ClO₃)₃ is probably a low melting compound. However, all the attempted methods to isolate the solid, met with no success.

References

1. A. BURCAT, I. PALLY and M. STEINBERG, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **30** 41.
2. M. R. UDUPA and G. K. RAMACHANDRA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1974, **9**, 427.
3. M. R. UDUPA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1975, **12**, 165.
4. M. R. UDUPA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1975, **13**, 349.
5. M. R. UDUPA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1975, **13**, 246.
6. A. I. VOGEL, 'A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis', Longman Inc., 1978.
7. C. K. JORGENSEN, 'Absorption Spectra and Chemical Bonding in Complexes', Addison-Wesely, Massachusetts, 1962.
8. N. T. McDEVIT and W. L. BAUN, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1964, **20**, 799.
9. 'Inorganic Index to the Powder Diffraction File', JCPDS, 1971.

Ligational Behaviour of *o*-Aminobenzoylhydrazine towards some Transition Metal Ions

S. GHOSH* and T. K. BANDYOPADHYAY

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 19 November 1979,
accepted 25 December 1979

ACIDHYDRAZIDES and their derivatives have received considerable attention because of their potentiality as versatile coordinating agents^{1,2} as well as their antibacterial activity³⁻⁵. Extensive search of literature showed that no work has been done on the metal chelates of *o*-aminobenzoylhydrazine (LH), a potential tridentate ligand. We have also observed that this ligand molecule is capable of inhibiting the growth of some strains of tuberculosis mycobacteria⁶. In the present communication, we wish to make a preliminary report on the chelating behaviour of *o*-aminobenzoylhydrazine (LH) towards Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) ions. With Cu(II) salts, both mono- and bis-chelates have been isolated; whereas, the Co(II) and Ni(II) salts forms only 1 : 2 type complexes. In all these cases the ligand behaved as a neutral one. All the metal complexes have been prepared by reacting the metal salts with the ligand in warm aqueous-ethanol in 1 : 2 proportion, when microcrystalline complexes separated slowly. For the preparation of 1 : 1 type Cu(II) complexes, 1 : 1 molar ratio of the metal salt and the ligand was used. The analytical data and magnetic moment values of some of the representative complexes are given in Table 1.

The effective magnetic moment values for the complexes, Cu(LH)₂X₂.4H₂O (X = NO₃, $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄²⁻), fall in the range of distorted octahedral Cu(II) complexes⁷. On the other hand, the Cu(II) complexes of the formula Cu(LH)X₂.4H₂O (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄²⁻), exhibit subnormal magnetic moment values. The Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes show paramagnetism corresponding to two and three unpaired electrons respectively, in an octahedral environment^{8,9}. The electronic spectral data for all the complexes are also indicative of octahedral disposition of the donor sites around the metal ions.

The ligand molecule possess three potential donor sites namely, the carbonyl oxygen, the hydrazinic -NH₂ and the ring NH₂ groups. The i.r. spectrum of the ligand in KBr exhibits bands at 3420 cm⁻¹ and 3250 cm⁻¹. The first one may be assigned to the stretching vibration of the ring -NH₂¹⁰ and the second one to the superimposed stretching vibrations of -NH bands of the hydrazinic amino and imino groups. The lowering of the band at 3250 cm⁻¹ by 10-50 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes is suggestive of hydrazinic -NH₂ - coordination to the metal ions. The ligand shows a strong absorption band at 1655 cm⁻¹ (amide I band), which

*For communication.